

STUDIES IN THE NEGATIVELY CHARGED COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS OF VARIOUS FERRIC SALTS. PART IV.

NEGATIVELY CHARGED FERRIC TUNGSTATE SOL

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Negatively charged ferric tungstate sols have been prepared by dispersing freshly precipitated ferric tungstate by caustic soda, in presence of glucose or glycerine. The empirical formula of the sol, peptised in presence of glucose is $13\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and that of the sol peptised in presence of glycerine is $17\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Various other characteristics of the sols have also been investigated.

In previous parts Musharan and Prakash (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 23, 111, 391, 413) studied in details the composition and various properties of negatively charged ferric vanadate, borate and molybdate sols. In this paper we have described our experimental results with negatively charged ferric tungstate sols.

It has been observed by one of the present authors (Musharan, *Current Sci.*, 1946, 14, 200) that when sodium tungstate is added to ferric chloride solution containing glucose, a yellowish white precipitate of ferric tungstate is obtained, which dissolves on shaking if ferric chloride be in excess. If this clear mixture be purified by dialysis and coagulated by electrolytes, it sets to a transparent jelly with slight opalescence. Evidently the jelly has come out of the positively charged ferric tungstate sol. Now we have observed that the ferric tungstate precipitate can be peptised by caustic soda in presence of glucose or glycerine, and the bright red sol thus obtained carries over the negative charge. The idea of peptisation can be had from the following figures.

Ferric chloride solution (1 to 3 c.c.) corresponding to 30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre), when mixed with 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of 10% sodium tungstate solution in presence of 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of 20% glucose solution, requires 1.6 to 3.7 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about the complete peptisation in half an hour.

The same ferric chloride solution (1.0 to 3.0 c.c.), when mixed with 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of 10% sodium tungstate solution in presence of 1.0 to 3.0 c.c. of glycerine, requires 1.1 to 3.8 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about the complete peptisation in half an hour.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sol A was prepared by mixing 50 c.c. of a ferric chloride solution (corresponding to 30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre), 50 c.c. of 10% sodium tungstate solution, 50 c.c. of 20% glucose solution and 70 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution. The total volume was kept 250 c.c. The sol was dialysed for 5 days.

Sol B was prepared by mixing 50 c.c. of ferric chloride (of the same strength), 50 c.c. of 10% sodium tungstate solution, 25 c.c. of glycerine and 67.5 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution. The total volume was raised to 250 c.c. The sol was dialysed for 3 days.

Composition of the Sols

The amount of tungsten in a given volume of the sol was estimated as WO_3 . To a known volume of the sol was added Merck's concentrated hydrochloric acid and a little nitric acid and the solution was warmed. Tungsten was thus precipitated as tungstic acid. A small amount of NH_4Cl was added to prevent the formation of colloidal tungstic acid, and the solution was again heated. The tungstic acid was allowed to settle down and then filtered. The precipitate was ignited slowly in an open platinum crucible and the residue was weighed as WO_3 . After precipitation and filtration of the tungstic acid, concentrated ammonia was added to the filtrate and iron was precipitated as $Fe(OH)_3$. This was ignited in a platinum crucible and estimated as Fe_2O_3 . The amount of tungsten in the combined state with iron was found by coagulating a known amount of the sol cataphoretically and also by potassium chloride, the coagulum was in both the cases separately collected, washed, and estimated for tungsten as WO_3 . The combined iron corresponding to this amount of tungstate was calculated on the assumption that ferric tungstate was $Fe_2(WO_4)_3$. The rest of the iron must be present as hydrated ferric oxide. From the ratio of the free to the combined iron the empirical formula of the sol was calculated.

TABLE I

Per litre.	Sol A.		Per litre	Sol B.	
	Glucose sol	Glycerine sol		Glucose sol	Glycerine sol
Total iron	3.5880 g.	2.8883 g.	Free iron	3.3378 g.	2.7279 g.
Total tungstate (WO_3)	1.9600	2.7200	Viscosity of sol (30°)	0.00931	0.00868
Combined tungstate (WO_3)	1.5600	1.0000	Viscosity of water (30°)	0.00803	0.00808
Free tungstate (WO_3)	0.4000	1.7200	Water bound	0.03826	0.38500
Combined iron	0.2502	0.1604			
Empirical formula	13 $Fe_2O_3 \cdot Fe_2(WO_4)_3 \cdot H_2O$.		17 $Fe_2O_3 \cdot Fe_2(WO_4)_3 \cdot 15H_2O$.		

The sols were coagulated cataphoretically and by *N*/2-KCl, centrifuged, and the pH values of the supernatant liquids were determined by Hildebrand hydrogen electrode. The following pH values are recorded.

Glucose sol(A)	7.32 (KCl coagulated)	Glycerin sol (B)	76.2 (KCl coagulated)
	7.39 (Cataphoretically coagulated)		7.63 (Cataphoretically coagulated)

Specific Conductivities of the Sols

In the following table are recorded our observations on the conductivities of these sols at different temperatures, and dilutions and also the values on ageing.

TABLE II A

Sp. conductivity at diff. dilutions (30°).

Dilution.	Sp. condy. in mho		Dilution	Sp. condy. in mho.	
	Sol A.	Sol B		Sol A.	Sol B.
Sol (X) (original)	12.30×10^{-4}	25.20×10^{-4}	X/2	6.16×10^{-4}	13.46×10^{-4}
5X/6	10.26	21.42	X/3	4.16	9.32
2X/3	8.21	17.26	X/6	2.16	6.08

TABLE II B

Sp. conductivity on ageing (30°).

Date.	Sp. conductivity on ageing (30°).		Date.	Sp. conductivity on ageing (30°).	
4.3.45	12.30×10^{-4}	—	24.3.45	12.39×10^{-4}	25.71×10^{-4}
12.3.45	12.34	—	25.4.45	—	The sol settles down
14.3.45	—	25.20×10^{-4}	27.3.45	12.43	—
17.3.45	—	25.42	6.6.45	12.43	—
21.3.45	—	25.68	2.7.45	12.46	—

TABLE II C

Sp. conductivity at different temperatures.

Temp.	Glucose sol A		Glycerine sol B	
	Sp. condy.	Diff. per 5°	Sp. condy.	Diff. per 5°.
40°	14.70×10^{-4} mhos	1.20	29.86×10^{-4} mhos	2.34
35	13.50	1.20	27.52×10^{-4}	2.32
30	12.30	1.20	25.20	2.32
25	11.10	1.20	22.89	2.33
20	9.90	1.20	20.56	—
Temp of zero conductance (extrapolated)	-19.5°		-24.5°	
Temp. coefficient per 1°	0.240		0.466	

From the above table it appears that in the case of the glucose sol A, the sp. conductivity runs proportional to dilutions, whilst in the case of the glycerine sol B, those at various dilutions are always higher than those computed on the basis of dilutions. The higher values of conductivity evidently suggest hydrolysis of the sol. The sp. conductivities of both the sols increase with age. The sp. conductivity-temperature curves are straight lines.

Extinction Coefficients of the Sols

Extinction coefficients were determined by Nutting's spectrophotometer at different dilutions and at different wave-lengths. (X stands for the original undiluted sol).

TABLE III.

Wave-lengths	Glucose sol (A)				Glycerine sol (B)			
	Dilutions				Dilutions			
	X	X/2	X/4	X/8	X	X/2	X/4	X/8
5000 Å	—	3.66	1.83	0.93	—	—	—	—
5200	4.64	2.32	1.16	0.58	3.12	2.09	1.44	1.33
54.0	2.86	1.44	0.72	0.36	2.54	1.44	1.13	0.88
5600	1.84	0.92	0.46	0.43	1.79	1.06	0.70	0.44
5800	1.25	0.62	0.31	0.16	1.14	0.66	0.59	0.30
6000	0.85	0.43	0.22	0.11	0.80	0.50	0.47	0.22
6200	0.68	0.34	0.17	0.09	0.61	0.44	0.43	0.14
6400	0.50	0.26	0.12	0.06	0.47	0.36	0.33	0.11
6600	0.40	0.20	0.09	0.05	0.38	0.26	0.20	0.09
6800	0.28	0.14	0.07	0.03	0.29	0.19	0.13	0.07

A scrutiny of the above table shows that in the case of the glucose sol A, Beer's law is almost rigidly followed, *i.e.*, the extinction coefficients are approximately proportional to the dilutions. In the case of sol B, the extinction coefficients are always higher than those computed on the basis of dilution. The hydrolysis of ferric tungstate under these conditions has no doubt caused deviations in the extinction coefficients-dilution relationship (*cf.* results on the sp. conductivities at different dilutions in Table IIA).

Coagulation of the Sols

In the following table are recorded the minimum amounts of electrolytes necessary to coagulate 1 c.c. of the sols in a total volume of 10 of c.c., the time allowed in each case being 30 minutes.

TABLE IV

Electrolytes.	Sol A.		Sol B.	
	Amount necessary to coagulate		Amount necessary to coagulate	
N/2-NaCl	2.70 c.c.	2.00 c.c.	N/250-Ba(NO ₃) ₂	2.70 c.c.
N/2-KCl	2.10	1.40	N/250-Sr(NO ₃) ₂	3.10
N/2-KNO ₃	2.10	1.40	N/250-AlCl ₃	1.50
N/2-KBr	2.10	1.40		1.30

The coagulating power of the ions thus falls in the following series: NaCl < KCl, KBr, KNO₃ < Sr(NO₃)₂ < Ba(NO₃)₂ < AlCl₃

The effect of dilution on the coagulation values has also been investigated.

TABLE V

Total volume = 10 c.c.

Electrolytes.	Glucose sol A			Glycerine sol B		
	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.
N/2-NaCl	2.70	2.80	2.90	2.00	2.50	3.00
N/2-KCl	2.10	2.20	2.30	1.40	1.48	1.58
N/2-KNO ₃	2.10	2.20	2.30	1.40	1.48	1.58

From this table it is evident that the sol obeys the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour with dilution. The dilute sol requires less amount of electrolyte to coagulate it in a specified time.

Positively charged Ferric Tungstate Sols

It was reported by Varma and Prakash (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 205, 241) that when sodium tungstate was added to a solution of ferric chloride, the precipitate of ferric tungstate formed was only slightly peptised by adding ferric chloride in excess, but the peptisation was sufficient to give a clear sol if glycerine or glucose was used as a peptising agent. The sol thus formed bears a positive charge. In Table VI are given our results on the compositions of some positively charged ferric tungstate sols.

Sol A was prepared by mixing 50 c.c. of ferric chloride solution (corresponding to 69.84 g. of Fe₂O₃ per litre), 20 c.c. of 10% Na₂WO₄ solution and 25 c.c.

of 20% glucose solution. The mixture was vigorously shaken and then dialysed for 3 days.

Sol B was prepared by mixing 50 c.c. of ferric chloride solution (corresponding to 69.84 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre) 40 c.c. of 10% Na_2WO_4 solution and 10 c.c. of 20% glycerine solution. The mixture was vigorously shaken and dialysed for 3 days.

Estimations of iron and tungsten were made in the same manner as in the case of negatively charged ferric tungstate sols.

TABLE VI

Per litre.	Sol A.	Sol B.
Total iron	7.8225 g.	7.5815 g.
Combined tungstate	8.8000	16.1700
Combined iron	1.3310	2.5930
Free iron	6.4915	4.9885
Viscosity of sol	0.00855	0.00860
Viscosity of water	0.00803	0.00803
Water, bound	0.2249	0.2913
Empirical formula	$5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
Sol (A) contained	2.9710 g. of Cl' per litre.	
Sol (B) contained	2.9530 g. of Cl' per litre.	

DISCUSSION

When sodium tungstate is added to ferric chloride, ferric tungstate is precipitated according to the following equation,

The precipitated ferric tungstate, though not easily peptised by caustic soda alone, goes to form a clear negatively charged ferric tungstate sol, if peptised in presence of glucose or glycerine by caustic soda. During the course of peptisation in presence of alkali ions, a part of ferric tungstate precipitated may undergo hydrolysis according to the following equation,

During the course of dialysis ferric tungstate further hydrolyses and the composition corresponds to higher ferric oxide content:

The negatively charged sols of ferric tungstate investigated in this paper had the following compositions. For comparison the compositions of some positively charged sols are also given:

Negatively charged sols:

- (a) $13\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
 (b) $17\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Positively charged sols:

- (a) $5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
 (b) $2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{WO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

From the compositions given here, it is clear that the positively charged sols contain proportionately a higher content of ferric tungstate. The negatively charged sols were prepared mainly in the alkaline medium. Even after dialysis the pH of the supernatant liquids obtained after the coagulation of the sols lie between 7.32 and 7.63. The sols prepared were sufficiently alkaline. This accounts for the larger proportion of ferric oxide in the negatively charged sols.

As discussed in Part I (*loc. cit.*) it will be interesting to study the temperature coefficients of conductivity of negatively charged ferric tungstate sols. The temperature coefficients are given below with the corresponding conductivities at 35°.

	Conductivity at 35°.	Temp co eff. per 1°
Sol (A)	13.50 x 10 ⁻⁴ moha	0.210
Sol (B)	27.52	0.466

The temperature coefficient of sol A is thus 1.77% of the conductance at 35°, and that of sol B is 1.69% of the conductance at 35°. The temperature coefficients are thus always less than 2% of the conductances at 35°

C O N C L U S I O N

From the results recorded in the foregoing tables the following observations may be summarised.

(i) The conductivity of the glucose sol is very approximately proportional to the dilution, whilst the conductivity of the glycerine sol does not decrease in the same proportion as the dilution. This deviation from the dilution rule indicates marked hydrolysis of the glycerine sol.

(ii) The electrical conductivities of both the glucose and glycerine sols are linear functions of temperatures. The temperatures of zero conductance lie between -19.5° and -24.5°.

(iii) The temperature coefficients of conductivities per 1° of the sols are always less than 2% of the conductances at 35°.

(iv) The results on the ageing effect on the conductivities of the sols show increase of conductivities as the time proceeds.

(v) The changes in the extinction coefficients with dilution show that whilst Beer's law is observed in the case of glucose sols, it is not followed in the case of glycerine sol. The extinction coefficient in the case of glycerine sol does not decrease in the same proportion as the dilution indicating hydrolysis of the sol on dilution.

(vi) The sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for the coagulation of electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour on dilution.

(vii) The pH values of the dispersion medium lie between 7.22 and 7.63 showing that the sols are slightly basic owing to the stabilising hydroxide ions.